

Collaboration networks and their effects on open access uptake: Analyzing how authors of a Canadian federal science department comply with mandates

Chantal Ripp¹ and Stefanie Haustein²

¹chantal.ripp@uottawa.ca

University of Ottawa, School of Information Studies, Scholarly Communications Lab, 55 Laurier Avenue East,
K1N 6N5, Ottawa, Ontario, (Canada)

²stefanie.haustein@uottawa.ca

University of Ottawa, School of Information Studies, Scholarly Communications Lab, 55 Laurier Avenue East,
K1N 6N5, Ottawa, Ontario, (Canada)

Université du Québec à Montréal, Observatoire des Sciences et des Technologies (OST), Centre
Interuniversitaire de Recherche sur la Science et la Technologie (CIRST), CP 8888, Succ. Centre-Ville, H3C
3P8, Montréal, Québec, (Canada)

Abstract

This research-in-progress paper presents the results of an exploratory analysis investigating the effect of institutional collaborations on compliance with mandated open access (OA) policies by Canadian federal science-based departments. More specifically, we explore how authors affiliated with Agriculture & Agri Food Canada (AAFC) follow the Canadian government's *Roadmap for Open Science* to make publications OA (gold, hybrid, green) when publishing with or without national and international collaborators. Using VOSviewer, collaboration patterns and OA compliance is visualized. Preliminary findings show that AAFC complies less with the federal OA mandate when publishing alone or with co-authors from academia and OA uptake is highest when they collaborate with other government partners.

Introduction

To tackle complex challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and public health crises, many funders, governments and international organizations argue that science needs to be more transparent, accessible and inclusive. OECD and UNESCO have released recommendations on open science to make science more open (OECD Council, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). At the same time, national governments and public funding agencies have gradually adopted policies that promote open science principles, including open access (OA) to scientific articles and access to data from research. The practice of open science is firmly secured in the values of sharing and collaboration to advance opportunities for innovation and participation in the co-creation of knowledge (UNESCO, 2021).

Within the Canadian context, commitments to open science have been formalized through the release of National Action Plans on Open Government (2012-2020) (Government of Canada, 2020). In February 2020, Canada's Chief Science Advisor released the federal *Roadmap for Open Science* with the overarching goal of making federal science openly available to all. Federal science-based departments and agencies (SBDA) were required to create action plans on how they intended to implement the recommendations in the Roadmap (Office of the Chief Science Advisory, 2020). At the time of this study, eleven departments, including Agriculture & Agri Foods Canada (AAFC), had published their action plans. AAFC was selected as the basis of this study as they had also published their policy on scientific publications that stipulates OA requirements apply when the (co-)corresponding author is an AAFC employee (AAFC, 2021).

OA to scientific articles authored or co-authored by a federal researcher was a central part of the roadmap. It also endorsed the principle that open science enables collaboration between and among intramural and extramural science communities (2020). However, it is not known whether extramural collaborations with partners that do not have any or different OA mandates affect the uptake and route to OA (green, gold, hybrid).

Establishing policies, however, is only a first step towards increasing the adoption of open science. As Lariviere and Sugimoto (2018) have shown, monitoring funded research outputs significantly increases OA compliance. Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC), with support from other federal SBDAs, committed to publishing yearly reporting measures on the implementation of open science by SBDAs (Government of Canada, 2020). These reports however, do not clearly depict the bibliometric methods used, the scope and inclusion criteria, and obscures the relative importance of the players in research collaborations. The results and insights drawn from monitoring exercises inform resource allocation, strategic initiatives, and organizational policies (SBDA Open Science Metrics Working Group, 2021).

Within the literature, it is ubiquitously acknowledged that performing and publishing research is often highly collaborative (Marušić et al.2011; Olechnicka et al.2018). As highlighted, while there are guidelines and studies on monitoring exercises on open science trends at various levels of aggregation (e.g. institution, region, country) and the counting methods to be considered, few studies critically examine how research collaboration patterns out of the university sector influence engagement in OA publishing. The main goal of this study is to provide methodological insights on the use of co-authorship networks to examine collaboration patterns and uptake of OA for the federal department Agriculture & Agri Food Canada (AAFC). Hence, the RIP is exploratory and descriptive, with the objective to set the basis for more specific research questions that can be developed in the future in an informed way regarding uptake and type of OA by federal SBDAs. An analysis at the level of the institution examining OA rates taking collaboration with various sectors into account complements previous studies (Huang et al., 2020; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020) related to OA uptake.

Methods

Bibliometrics measures and social network analysis (SNA) were used to analyze bibliographic metadata to examine collaboration patterns and OA trends. SNA is a method that emerged from sociology and graph theory that permits the visualization of networks using co-authorship as a proxy of collaboration (Fonseca et al.2017; Leite & Pinho, 2016). Bibliographic data was retrieved from Clarivate's Web of Science (WoS) Core collection. The sample was limited to articles and reviews associated with researchers affiliated to AAFC for the reference period 2017 to 2021 to observe trends and changes from before and after the roadmap and associated action plans were taking effect. OA status, including Gold, Hybrid, and Green OA, is provided at the article-level in WoS based on information provided by Unpaywall. Within the OA status, article-level OA of all versions are identified when multiple versions of an article are available (e.g., gold, hybrid, green).

Three types of OA, and a closed category, are considered in this study (adapted from Piwowar et al., 2018), identified as follows:

- Gold: Identified as having a Creative Commons (CC) license by Unpaywall.
- Green: Toll-access on the publisher page, but there is a free copy in an OA repository.
- Hybrid: Free under an open license in a toll-access journal.
- Closed: All other articles.

Although Bronze OA status was provided in the metadata, this OA type was grouped with "closed" access as it represents (often temporarily) free-to-read articles that do not have a reuse license and can therefore not be considered fully OA at the end of a defined period of time.

Corresponding authorship status, which determines whether or not AAFC's OA mandate applies, is provided in the bibliographic export. WoS also provides an affiliation-enhanced field that aggregates variants of an institution's name to facilitate discovery and retrieval. Although the enhanced affiliation information was provided in the data extract, organization names were still required to be cleaned. This was done using the VOSviewer thesaurus function. A known limitation for this study is that not all publications authored by a federal researcher are captured for analysis, if they are not indexed in WoS. Institutions were classified as academic, corporate, government, health, and other based on a typology by Godin (2002) to analyze to what extent collaborations with co-authors from different sectors influence OA compliance.

Preliminary findings

Between 2017 and 2021, researchers affiliated with AAFC authored or co-authored 5,032 publications. During this time, the proportion of papers whereby AAFC is a corresponding or co-corresponding author steadily decreased from 50.4% in 2017 to 42.1% in 2021. At the same time, the proportion of collaborations with extramural researchers, that is to say with an institution outside of AAFC, trended upwards from 83.6% in 2017 to 86.9% in 2021. Notably, collaborations have been a factor in increasing the share of research output attributed to AAFC. Table 1 lists the number of publications for each type of organization AAFC collaborates with on at least 3 publications, and the OA rate for Gold, Hybrid, and Green OA as well as any of the three types of OA (any OA). It should be noted that the any OA category is not a sum of the individual categories, but counts each OA paper once, even if it was disseminated openly via multiple OA paths (e.g. Gold and Green).

Table 1: Research collaboration types and percentage of OA publications

	Total pubs		Any OA		Gold OA		Hybrid OA		Green OA	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Total	5,032	100%	2,649	52.6%	1,466	29.1%	482	9.6%	1,943	38.6%
AAFC no collab.	704	14.0%	316	44.9%	158	22.4%	76	10.8%	197	28.0%
AAFC Corr. Auth.	2,254	44.8%	1,186	52.6%	645	28.6%	231	10.2%	833	37.0%
<i>Extramural collab (min 3 docs)</i>										
AAFC-Academic	4,103	81.5%	2,037	49.6%	1,239	30.2%	394	9.6%	1,666	40.6%
<i>Top 5 academic collaborating institutions</i>										

uni of saskatchewan	457	11.1%	249	54.5%	143	31.3%	49	10.7%	206	45.1%
uni of guelph	395	9.6%	184	46.6%	121	30.6%	33	8.4%	152	38.5%
uni of alberta	314	7.7%	141	44.9%	85	27.1%	21	6.7%	118	37.6%
uni of manitoba	311	7.6%	140	45.0%	85	27.3%	32	10.3%	118	37.9%
laval university	260	6.3%	108	41.5%	64	24.6%	32	12.3%	77	29.6%
AAFC-Government	953	18.9%	548	57.5%	311	32.6%	118	12.4%	479	50.3%
Other SBDAs	301	31.6%	164	54.5%	100	33.2%	33	11.0%	140	46.5%
AAFC-Health	63	1.3%	34	54.0%	14	22.2%	10	15.9%	26	41.3%
AAFC-Corporate	60	1.2%	31	51.7%	24	40.0%	6	10.0%	29	48.3%
AAFC-Other	827	16.4%	481	58.2%	259	31.3%	102	12.3%	421	50.9%

Co-authorship networks and OA type

Of the 5,032 publications, 52.6% (n=2,649) of the publications were available in at least one form of OA. AAFC collaborated with a total of 1,999 unique organizations between 2017-2021. Organizations were grouped into 80 clusters, with AAFC found in cluster 13. The largest cluster contains 732 organizations that were primarily international organizations. AAFC's strongest collaborations in the network, as depicted by node size (weighted by total link strength) is University of Saskatchewan (n=457 publication, cluster 27), University of Guelph (n=395 publications; cluster 32), University of Alberta (n=314 publications; cluster 22), University of Manitoba (n=311 publications, cluster 25), and Laval University (n=260; cluster 19).

Figures 1 below depict the proportion of articles co-authored by researchers affiliated with the institutions whose articles are either Gold, Hybrid, Green or Any OA. Within the network, a larger proportion of gold OA publications is as a result of collaborations with international partners. With respect to AAFC's closest collaborations with Canadian academic partners, the share of publications that are gold OA on average is less than 30%. Whereas for the share of publications that are deposited in green OA with AAFC top five collaborating Canadian academic institutions rises to an average of over 37%.

Figure 1a: Gold OA, AAFC 30% of publications

Figure 1b: Hybrid OA, AAFC 6% of publications

Figure 1c: Green OA, AAFC 38% publication

Figure 1d: Any OA, AAFC 48% of publication

Figure 1: Institutional co-authorship network, whereby the colour of the nodes is defined by the rate of OA. Lowest score of 0 implies no publications by that institution have been made OA, and the highest score of 1 implies all publications have been made OA.

Discussion

The descriptive and network analyses have revealed some interesting insights relating to patterns of collaboration by the AAFC department with respect to OA status. AAFC conducted consultations among its researchers as part of the development of its action plan on open science that determined that gold OA was the predominant form of OA used by AAFC researchers and identified as a limitation to OA publishing (2021). As such, AAFC identified the prioritization of developing infrastructure to support green OA publishing routes by developing and deploying an OA archive for federal science publications (AAFC, 2021). By taking a closer examination of OA practices by AAFC as a single institution author, corresponding author, and patterns of collaboration, we identified that gold OA is in fact not the dominant form and a larger proportion of publications are already being made open by green OA.

Nearly 80% of publications feature at least one academic partner, but only 49.6% of these publications are OA. Within the academic context in particular, knowledge exchange is still heavily influenced by researchers' aspirations to publish in highly cited journals (Butler et al., 2022; Chataway et al., 2017). While AAFC open science action plan identifies collaboration as

a core principle of open science, it fails to identify how it will encourage adoption of OA with its collaborators (2021). When it comes to shared decision-making with external collaborators, research groups would benefit from additional awareness of the department's commitment to OA, along with tools and guidance to assist in these processes.

Collecting and analyzing data play a powerful role to inform the implementation and evaluation of the impact of policy measures. In a collaboration focused era, it is simply not enough to understand the rate of OA of organizations to determine rankings, but rather understand who that organization collaborates with and how that may influence engaging in open science practices, particularly when those institutions have different mandates or research agendas. These insights can strongly affect decision-making and resource allocation to support an organization in making their research results open. While the preliminary research highlights some interesting preliminary findings, more rigorous analysis is required to further reveal the underlying connection between the collaboration structure and the OA compliance. Future work on this project will examine collaboration patterns and OA for the ten other SBDAs, as well as data sharing practices to inform a broader government open science agenda.

References

- Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada. (2021, April 14). *Policy on Science and Technology Publications*. <https://agriculture.canada.ca/en/agricultural-science-and-innovation/agriculture-and-agri-food-canada-science-integrity-policy/agriculture-and-agri-food-canada-policy-science-and-technology-publications>
- Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada. (2021, November 16). *Open Science Action Plan 2021-2022 to 2025-2026 – Enable and Equip*. <https://agriculture.canada.ca/en/about-our-department/agriculture-and-agri-food-canadas-open-science-action-plan-2021-2022-2025-2026-enable-and-equip>
- Butler, L.-A., Matthias, L., Simard, M.-A., Mongeon, P., & Haustein, S. (2022). The oligopoly's shift to open access publishing: How for-profit publishers benefit from gold and hybrid article processing charges. *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of CAIS / Actes Du Congrès Annuel De l'ACSI*. <https://doi.org/10.29173/cais1262>
- Chataway, J., Parks, S., & Smith, E. (2017). How Will Open Science Impact on University-Industry Collaboration? *Foresight and STI Governance*, 11(2), 44-53. <https://doi.org/10.17323/2500-2597.2017.2.44.53>
- Fonseca, Fernandes, E., & Fonseca, M. V. A. (2017). Collaboration in science and technology organizations of the public sector: A network perspective. *Science & Public Policy*, 44(1), 37–49. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scw013>
- Godin, B., Doré, C., & Larivière, V. (2002). The Production of Knowledge in Canada: Consolidation and Diversification. *Journal of Canadian Studies*, 37(3), 56–70. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jcs.37.3.56>
- Government of Canada. (2020, October 09). *Canada's 2018-2020 National Action Plan on Open Government*. <https://open.canada.ca/en/content/canadas-2018-2020-national-action-plan-open-government>
- Huang, C.-K. (Karl), Neylon, C., Hosking, R., Montgomery, L., Wilson, K. S., Ozaygen, A., & Brookes-Kenworthy, C. (2020). Evaluating the impact of open access policies on research institutions. *ELife*, 9, e57067. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.57067>
- Larivière, V., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2018). Do authors comply when funders enforce open access to research? *Nature (London)*, 562(7728), 483–486. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-07101-w>
- Leite, & Pinho, I. (2016). What Do We Measure by Evaluating Research Collaboration Networks? In *Evaluating Collaboration Networks in Higher Education Research* (pp. 57–77). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45225-8_5
- Marušić, A., Bošnjak, L., & Jerončić, A. (2011). A Systematic Review of Research on the Meaning, Ethics and Practices of Authorship across Scholarly Disciplines. *PLOS ONE*, 6(9), e23477. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0023477>

- Piwowar, H., Priem, J., Larivière, V., Alperin, J. P., Matthias, L., Norlander, B., Farley, A., West, J., & Haustein, S. (2018). The state of OA: A large-scale analysis of the prevalence and impact of Open Access articles. *PeerJ*, 6, e4375. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4375>
- OECD Council. (2021, January 20). *Recommendation of the OECD Council concerning Access to Research Data from Public Funding*. <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/recommendation-access-to-research-data-from->
- Office of the Chief Science Advisory. (February 2020). *Roadmap for Open Science*. <https://science.gc.ca/site/science/en/office-chief-science-advisor/open-science/roadmap-open-science>
- Olechnicka, A., Ploszaj, A., & Celińska-Janowicz, D. (2018). *The Geography of Scientific Collaboration (First edition)*. Routledge.
- Robinson Garcia, N., et al. “Open Access Uptake by Universities Worldwide.” *PeerJ* (San Francisco, CA), vol. 2020, no. 7, 2020, pp. e9410–e9410, <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9410>
- SBDA Open Science Metrics Working Group. (2021). *The 2020 annual report on the federal progress in implementing open science and its benefits (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5730518>
- UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (SC-PCB-SPP/2021/UROS)*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>